

Analysis of the Influence of Fuel Zone Radius Variation in HTR-PM Fuel Pebbles on Reactor Core Calculation

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803771

ABSTRACT

As a key component of Pebble-Bed High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (PB-HTGRs), the fuel pebble significantly influences core reactivity. The geometric dimensions of the fuel pebble, particularly the fuel zone radius, are crucial parameters in core design and analysis. This study systematically investigates the impact of the fuel zone radius variation on neutronics and thermal-hydraulic performance in the HTR-PM. Using the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX and the PB-HTGR core analysis code NECP-Panda, this study generated homogenized cross-section libraries for fuel pebbles with different fuel zone radii and performed simulations under both initial criticality and equilibrium core conditions. Results indicate that a reduction in the fuel zone radius introduces positive reactivity, which is owing to the weakening of the self-shielding effect and resonance absorption, as well as the enhanced neutron moderation from the thicker graphite shell. This change also influences the neutron spectrum and enhances the spatial self-shielding effect of the absorber, thereby leading to a decrease in the absorber worth. Furthermore, under equilibrium core conditions, fuel pebbles with smaller fuel zones lead to higher power peaking and elevated temperature peak compared to the pebbles with a larger fuel zone. Notably, the calculated control rod worth for models with smaller radii shows better agreement with measurement data than the design model, highlighting that the fuel zone radius is a sensitive parameter for core modeling and a potential factor in explaining calculation-to-measurement discrepancies. These findings provide insights into the relationship between fuel pebble radius and core performance, offering a useful reference for high-fidelity core modeling and the design optimization of PB-HTGRs.

Keywords: Fuel pebble, Fuel zone radius, Reactivity, HTR-PM, NECP-Panda

1. INTRODUCTION

The safety and economic viability of Pebble-Bed High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (PB-HTGRs) primarily rely on the design of their spherical fuel elements. Each spherical fuel element consists of tens of thousands of TRISO-structural ISOTropic (TRISO) coated fuel particles embedded within a graphite matrix. These TRISO particles are randomly dispersed in the fuel zone at the center of the element, which is encased in an outer graphite shell, as illustrated in Figure 1. Each TRISO particle comprises a fuel kernel surrounded by multiple layers of pyrolytic carbon (PyC) and silicon carbide (SiC). These coating layers effectively retain fission products, thereby ensuring reactor radiological safety and contributing to the inherent safety characteristics of PB-HTGRs [1].

The geometric parameters of the fuel pebble, especially the radius of the fuel zone, are key factors affecting core physics. Variations in the fuel zone radius alter the packing fraction of TRISO particles and the thickness of the graphite shell, which in turn influence neutron moderation, self-shielding effects, and ultimately core reactivity and power distribution. A systematic analysis of the influence of the fuel zone radius is therefore essential for accurate core calculation and analysis.

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Figure 1. Diagram of the spherical fuel element structure [2].

In this study, we employ the self-developed PB-HTGR core neutronics and thermal-hydraulics code NECP-Panda [3-4] to investigate the effects of fuel zone radius variation on HTR-PM [5] core physics and thermal-hydraulic parameters under both initial criticality and equilibrium core conditions. The research aims to expound the underlying mechanisms and improve the accuracy of core physics calculations, providing insights for the design optimization of PB-HTGRs.

2. CALCULATION MODEL

2.1. Description of Fuel Pebbles of HTR-PM

The fuel element of HTR-PM is a 6-cm-diameter sphere, whose structure is illustrated in Figure 1. The kernel of the internal TRISO particles consists of uranium dioxide (UO_2) and each fuel pebble is loaded with 7 grams of uranium. During the initial operation phase of HTR-PM, the core is primarily loaded with fuel pebbles of 4.2wt% U235/U , which are gradually replaced with 8.5wt% U235/U pebbles during the transition period.

To analyze the impact of the fuel zone radius, three representative values were selected for this study: 2.5 cm (as the baseline design reference), 2.3 cm, and 2.2 cm. With the overall pebble diameter remaining unchanged, a reduction in the fuel zone radius results in a corresponding increase in the thickness of the outer fuel-free graphite shell. Since the uranium loading per pebble remains constant, the packing fraction of TRISO particles within the fuel zone increases from the original ~7% (for 2.5 cm) to approximately 12.5% (for 2.2 cm). The parameters for the three fuel pebble types analyzed in this study are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Parameters of fuel pebbles with different fuel zone radii used in the analysis.

Parameters	Unit	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Fuel zone radius	cm	2.5	2.3	2.2
Thickness of graphite shell	cm	0.5	0.7	0.8
Packing fraction of TRISO particles	%	~7.0	~11.0	~12.5

2.2. Description of Calculation and Analysis Strategy

Based on the aforementioned geometric parameters of the fuel pebbles, the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX [6] is employed to perform modeling using the explicit modeling approach, generating homogenized cross-section libraries for the three types of fuel pebbles with different fuel zone radii.

Using the cross-section libraries of these three fuel pebble types, the NECP-Panda is applied to perform coupled neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations for the HTR-PM. The results were compared and analyzed across different fuel zone radii, encompassing key parameters such as core reactivity, absorber worth, discharge burnup, power peaking, and temperature peaking. The comparisons between the results from the different fuel zone radii enable the evaluation of the effects induced by fuel zone radius variation on core calculations.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This chapter investigates the influence of different fuel zone radii of fuel pebble on key reactor physical and thermal-hydraulic parameters in the HTR-PM at two distinct core states, including the initial criticality state and the equilibrium core state. NECP-Panda and the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX were used for calculational analysis, and all cross-section data utilized in these calculations were processed from the Evaluated Nuclear Data File ENDF/B-VIII.0 [7].

3.1. Initial Criticality State

First, under core conditions with a temperature of 30°C in an air atmosphere and both control rods and absorber balls positioned at the top of their channels, the effective multiplication factors (k_{eff}) were calculated for different loading heights of fuel. HTR-PM was initially loaded with 605 cm graphite pebbles at the bottom, topped by a mixture of fuel and graphite pebbles of varying heights. By substituting fuel pebbles with different fuel zone radii within mixed pebbles, the corresponding k_{eff} were obtained, as summarized in Table II. The reference values for this subsection were all obtained using the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX, configured to simulate 1,000,000 neutrons per generation for 1,000 total generations, with the first 100 generations being inactive generations. The results indicate that as the fuel zone radius decreases, the core k_{eff} exhibits an increasing trend, with all calculation deviations remaining within 250 pcm.

Table II. Calculation results of HTR-PM clean reactor loading for fuel pebbles with different fuel zone radii.

Loading height (cm)	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm		
	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)
220	0.94891	0.94923	32	0.95598	0.95629	31	0.95668	0.95714	46
250	0.98129	0.98292	163	0.98843	0.99023	180	0.98918	0.99111	193
275	1.00388	1.00524	136	1.01123	1.01267	143	1.01203	1.01361	158
300	1.02290	1.02360	70	1.03036	1.03113	77	1.03119	1.03211	92
330	1.03953	1.04162	209	1.04710	1.04926	216	1.04793	1.05026	233
385	1.06522	1.06661	139	1.07295	1.07440	145	1.07385	1.07544	159
440	1.08333	1.08467	134	1.09114	1.09256	112	1.09211	1.09363	152
495	1.09836	1.09841	5	1.10624	1.10638	14	1.10723	1.10747	24

Maintaining the core condition at 30°C in an air atmosphere and a loading height of 275 cm, the core k_{eff} and the reactivity worth of various absorber combinations were calculated, with the results displayed in Table III and Table IV. Compared to the reference values, the maximum deviation in k_{eff} was less than 200 pcm, and the relative deviation in the reactivity worth of the absorber combinations remained within 5%. Furthermore, it can be observed that the absorber worth exhibits a decreasing trend with the reduction of the fuel zone radius.

Table III. Comparison of k_{eff} with diverse absorber combinations with different fuel zone radii.

Input absorber	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm		
	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)
None	1.00388	1.00524	136	1.01123	1.01267	143	1.01203	1.01361	158
18 CRs	0.91560	0.91482	-78	0.92299	0.92215	-84	0.92375	0.92300	-75
24 CRs	0.89773	0.89766	-7	0.90516	0.90498	-18	0.90591	0.90584	-7
6 ABs	0.95165	0.95073	-88	0.95898	0.95803	-95	0.95979	0.95883	-96
24 CRs + 6 ABs	0.88170	0.88177	7	0.88906	0.88906	0	0.88989	0.88990	1

Table IV. Comparison of reactivity worth of diverse absorber combinations with different fuel zone radii.

Input absorber	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm		
	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)
None	0.00	0.00	/	0.00	0.00	/	0.00	0.00	/
18 CRs	9604.50	9832.39	2.37	9454.06	9693.38	2.53	9443.10	9685.09	2.56
24 CRs	11778.57	11922.02	1.22	11588.23	11750.83	1.40	11574.94	11737.50	1.40
6 ABs	5467.15	5703.60	4.32	5387.99	5632.01	4.53	5378.16	5636.50	4.80
24 CRs + 6 ABs	13803.76	13929.53	0.91	13588.88	13729.50	1.03	13562.14	13714.90	1.13

Subsequently, with the core atmosphere unchanged and the loading height increased to 385 cm, the 12 compensating rods and 6 regulating rods were synchronously inserted downward from the top of their respective channels. The k_{eff} and the corresponding reactivity worth for these 18 control rods at various insertion depths were calculated, as summarized in Table V and Table VI.

Table V. Comparison of k_{eff} with different insertion depth of 18 control rods with different fuel zone radii.

Insertion depth (cm)	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm		
	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (pcm)
0.0	1.06522	1.06661	139	1.07295	1.07440	145	1.07385	1.07544	159
177.3	1.06167	1.06339	172	1.06942	1.07117	175	1.07039	1.07220	181
232.3	1.05797	1.06012	215	1.06570	1.06791	221	1.06662	1.06890	228
287.3	1.04855	1.05120	265	1.05624	1.05894	270	1.05715	1.05996	281
342.3	1.03307	1.03601	294	1.04072	1.04374	302	1.04163	1.04474	311
397.3	1.01286	1.01574	288	1.02051	1.02338	287	1.02141	1.02423	278
452.3	0.99231	0.99426	195	0.99996	1.00188	192	1.00086	1.00275	189
507.3	0.97845	0.97886	41	0.98616	0.98653	37	0.98708	0.98747	39
562.3	0.97314	0.97279	-35	0.98085	0.98047	-38	0.98178	0.98142	-36
617.3	0.97203	0.97158	-45	0.97979	0.97927	-52	0.98077	0.98022	-55
672.3	0.97218	0.97158	-60	0.97990	0.97927	-63	0.98084	0.98022	-62
727.3	0.97234	0.97178	-56	0.98006	0.97947	-59	0.98096	0.98044	-52
1147.3	0.97271	0.97188	-83	0.98039	0.97957	-82	0.98133	0.98054	-79

Table VI. Comparison of worth with different insertion depth of 18 control rods with different fuel zone radii.

Insertion depth (cm)	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm			Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm		
	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)	NECP-MCX	NECP-Panda	Bias (%)
0.0	0.00	0.00	/	0.00	0.00	/	0.00	0.00	/
177.3	313.91	283.89	-9.56	307.64	280.66	-8.77	301.02	280.98	-6.65
232.3	643.32	573.96	-10.78	634.05	565.65	-10.79	631.23	568.92	-9.87
287.3	1492.48	1374.40	-7.91	1474.46	1358.85	-7.84	1471.08	1357.99	-7.69
342.3	2921.54	2769.18	-5.21	2886.34	2734.10	-5.27	2880.50	2732.40	-5.14
397.3	4853.01	4695.41	-3.25	4789.23	4640.21	-3.11	4781.00	4649.12	-2.76
452.3	6897.64	6822.33	-1.09	6803.01	6737.15	-0.97	6791.20	6740.56	-0.75
507.3	8325.14	8404.67	0.96	8202.44	8290.19	1.07	8186.04	8283.70	1.19
562.3	8882.82	9042.13	1.79	8751.40	8916.70	1.89	8732.94	8907.98	2.00
617.3	9000.16	9170.15	1.89	8861.70	9041.68	2.03	8837.83	9032.72	2.21
672.3	8984.29	9170.15	2.07	8850.24	9041.68	2.16	8830.55	9032.72	2.29
727.3	8967.36	9148.97	2.03	8833.58	9020.83	2.12	8818.08	9009.83	2.17
1147.3	8928.24	9138.38	2.35	8799.24	9010.40	2.40	8779.64	8999.42	2.50

There is a control rod reactivity worth measurement experiment being completed before the formal operation of HTR-PM #1 reactor module. The experiment was performed under core conditions of 142°C helium atmosphere and a mixed pebble loading height of 385 cm, measuring the reactivity worth of one compensating rod (C3) and one regulating rod (R4). Based on the experimental parameters, modeling and calculations were completed using NECP-Panda. The results were compared with the experimental measurements, as detailed in Table VII and Table VIII.

Table VII. Comparison of reactivity worth of C3 control rod with different fuel zone radii.

Date source	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm		Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm		Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm	
	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)
NECP-Panda	609.95	0.63	613.94	1.29	605.28	-0.14
Measurement	606.14					

Table VIII. Comparison of reactivity worth of R4 control rod with different fuel zone radii.

Date source	Fuel zone radius: 2.5 cm		Fuel zone radius: 2.3 cm		Fuel zone radius: 2.2 cm	
	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)	Worth (pcm)	Bias (%)
NECP-Panda	502.48	3.78	506.97	4.70	498.64	2.98
Measurement	484.20					

It can be observed that when the fuel zone radius is 2.2 cm, the calculated reactivity worth of C3 and R4 shows the better agreement with the experimental measurements. This indicates that the fuel zone radius is a critical parameter; its potential variation significantly influences the agreement between simulation and measurement.

Based on the aforementioned results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) Reducing the fuel zone radius will introduce positive reactivity. This is because the reduction in the radius of the fuel zone leads to a more compact spatial distribution of TRISO particles, thereby weakening the self-shielding effect and reducing resonance absorption. Moreover, the thickening of the surrounding graphite shell enhances neutron moderation. Both of these effects jointly result in more neutrons participating in effective fission, increasing reactivity.
- (2) Reducing the fuel zone radius leads to a decrease in reactivity worth of absorber. This reduction is primarily due to the thicker graphite shell, which increases the thermal neutron fraction in the core. The higher thermal flux, in turn, intensifies the spatial self-shielding effect at the surface of the inserted absorbers. Consequently, the volumetric absorption efficiency decreases, resulting in an overall reduction of the absorber worth.

3.2. Equilibrium Core State

The influence of the fuel zone radius is now extended from the initial criticality state to the equilibrium core conditions. This study establishes the simulation starting point as a full core loaded with fresh, high-enrichment (8.5wt% U-235/U) fuel pebbles. Refueling follows a 15-batch scheme, whereby 1/15 of the 8.5wt% U-235/U fuel pebbles are discharged and replaced with an equal number of fresh 8.5wt% U-235/U fuel pebbles in each cycle. The equilibrium core state is considered to be achieved when the core parameters stabilize under this continuous refueling pattern.

In the modeling of the HTR-PM core by NECP-Panda, the pebble bed is radially divided into four flow channels of equal volume. Axially, it is partitioned into 10 layers of equal height, resulting in a total of 40 distinct pebble bed regions. Within each region, the fuel pebbles are further grouped into 15 batches of equal volume. Given that the HTR-PM active core height is 11 m and contains approximately 420,000 pebbles, each axial layer in the NECP-Panda model comprises about 42,000 pebbles. Consequently, each refueling step replaces roughly 42,000 pebbles, corresponding to a simulation time step of 7 days at a discharge rate of 6,000 pebbles/day. Based on the fuel cycle mesh, the fuel pebble loaded at the top of the core requires 10 refueling steps to traverse the core height and be discharged from the bottom, which is counted as one complete pass. Therefore, after 150 refueling steps, the first batch of pebbles

originally in the top layer will have completed 15 full passes through the core. The simulation was configured for 300 refueling steps to ensure that all fuel pebbles loaded into the bed achieve this 15-pass cycle. The input parameters required for the calculation are defined according to the HTR-PM design values, as shown in Table IX. To isolate the neutronic effects of fuel zone radius variation, the depletion process was performed without a criticality search, maintaining the six regulating rods at a fixed insertion depth of 263 cm below the top of the active core.

Table IX. Key input parameters for equilibrium core simulation.

Parameters	Unit	Value
Thermal power	MW	250
Primary circuit pressure	MPa	7
Helium flow rate	kg/s	96
Bypass flow coefficient	%	10
Inlet helium temperature	°C	250
Refueling rate	pebbles/day	6000*

*: Total discharge rate including 5,600 recirculated and 400 fresh fuel pebbles.

Simulations were performed using 8.5wt% U-235/U fuel pebbles with fuel zone radii of 2.2 cm and 2.5 cm. The discharge burnup and maximum single-pebble power during this process are presented in Figure 2. These parameters exhibit significant variations in the first half of the simulation. However, in the latter half, the slope of the discharge burnup increment gradually decreases, and the maximum single-pebble power essentially stabilizes, indicating that the core has reached the equilibrium state.

As observed in the figure, compared to the 2.5 cm case, the fuel pebbles with a fuel zone radius of 2.2 cm generally exhibit a higher maximum single-pebble power, and a lower discharge burnup. The final discharge burnup for both types of fuel pebbles is approximately 88.4 GWd/tU, close to the design value of 90.0 GWd/tU.

Figure 2. Physical parameters variation curve during simulation.

Key physical and thermal-hydraulic parameters at the equilibrium core state are summarized in Table X. The introduction of positive reactivity due to the reduced fuel zone radius results in higher maximum single-pebble power and power density for the 2.2 cm case compared to the 2.5 cm case. Since the thermal conductivity of both fuel pebble types is nearly identical, the 2.2 cm case consequently exhibit a higher temperature peaking. The average helium outlet temperature shows minimal variation because it is primarily governed by the total core power and helium mass flow rate, which are held constant in these steady-state simulations; thus, the energy balance across the core remains consistent despite local power redistributions.

Table X. Comparison of the physical and thermal-hydraulic parameters.

Parameters	Unit	Fuel zone radius (cm)		Difference
		2.5	2.2	
Discharge burnup	GWd/tU	88.45	88.40	-0.05
Maximum single-pebble power	kW	1.65	1.73	+0.08
Maximum power density	W/cm ³	6.73	6.78	+0.05
Maximum fuel temperature	°C	937.02	939.47	+2.45
Maximum solid temperature	°C	926.28	930.51	+4.23
Maximum helium temperature	°C	922.05	922.18	+0.13
Average helium outlet temperature	°C	755.74	755.77	+0.03

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates the impact of fuel zone radius variation in fuel pebbles on core physics and thermal-hydraulic parameters, taking the HTR-PM as a case. Homogenized cross-section libraries for fuel pebble with different fuel zone radii were generated using the NECP-MCX. These were subsequently employed in core simulations performed with the NECP-Panda, analyzing the effects of fuel zone radius variation under both initial criticality and equilibrium core conditions.

The results demonstrate that a reduced fuel zone radius introduces positive reactivity due to the weakened self-shielding effect and enhanced neutron moderation from the thicker graphite shell. This change in geometry also alters the neutron energy spectrum and leads to a decrease in absorber worth. Equilibrium core simulations further indicate that fuel pebbles with a smaller fuel zone radius result in higher maximum single-pebble power, maximum power density, and temperature peaking compared to the fuel pebbles with the design radius. Furthermore, in the calculations of the reactivity worth for control rods C3 and R4, the results obtained using the fuel pebbles with a 2.2 cm fuel zone radius agree more closely with the experimental measurements. This closer agreement demonstrates the significant impact of pebble internal geometry on core physics, providing insights for high-fidelity modeling. These findings clarify the impact of fuel zone geometry on core parameters and provide valuable insights for the future design optimization of PB-HTGRs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is funded by the Science and Technology Project of the China Huaneng Group Co., Ltd., titled 'HNKJ22-H03 High Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor Nuclear Safety Key Operation Technology Research.'

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